

Spectral, thermal, XRD and biological studies on 4-(*p*-fluorophenyl)-2-aminothiazole[†]

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Abstract : 4-(*p*-Fluorophenyl)-2-aminothiazole (FPAT) was synthesized and characterized by spectral (UV-Visible, IR, NMR and Mass), thermal and X-ray diffraction analyses. From the TG-DTA curve, various kinetic parameters were calculated using Coats-Redfern (C.R.), MacCallum-Tanner (M.T.) and Horowitz-Metzger (H.M.) methods. The compound possesses a triclinic crystal system. It exhibits antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *K. pneumoniae*, and antifungal activity against *A. niger* and *C. albicans*.

Keywords : Aminothiazoles, thermal analysis, X-ray diffraction studies, biological activity.

Introduction

Thiazoles and their derivatives are well known as biologically active compounds¹⁻⁵. Thermal and XRD analysis of thiazoles and their derivatives are less studied aspects of thiazole chemistry. In the present communication, we report synthesis of 4-(*p*-fluorophenyl)-2-aminothiazole (FPAT), its characterization by spectral (UV-Visible, IR, NMR and Mass), thermal and X-ray diffraction analysis. It was tested for the evaluation of antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *K. pneumoniae* and antifungal activity against *A. niger* and *C. albicans*.

Results and discussion

The compound FPAT, C₉H₇FN₂S, is a colorless crystalline solid and melts at 114 °C. In the UV-Visible spectrum of FPAT, λ_{max} appears at around 303 nm. Its IR spectrum exhibits ν(NH₂), ν(C=N) and ν(C-S-C) modes at ~3314, ~1627 and ~585 cm⁻¹ respectively. The ¹H NMR spectrum of FPAT shows signals at (CDCl₃, TMS, δ ppm) 5.3 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.7 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.0 (2H, t, Ar-H), 6.6 (1H, s, H-thiazole).

GC-MS of FPAT was recorded. It shows the expected molecular ion peak at 194 (relative intensity 100%) confirming the molecular formula of FPAT as C₉H₇FN₂S. The molecular ion further undergoes rupture of thiazole moiety to give fragment : *m/z* 152 (relative intensity 81.5 %) (Scheme 1). The fragment (*m/z* 152) then undergoes decomposition to give smaller fragments, *m/z* (relative intensity %) : 122 (14.8), 108 (22.2), 107 (24), 95 (5.6), 75 (8.33), 57 (9.26), 50 (3.7).

Scheme 1

[†]This paper has been presented at 43rd Annual Convention of Chemists (2006) held at Dr. B. A. Marathwada University, Aurangabad, Maharashtra, India [ORG(OP)-54].

Thermal analysis :

The TG-DTA curve of FPAT is depicted in Fig. 1. FPAT undergoes decomposition in two stages. The first stage begins at 129.13 °C and ends at 244.37 °C. The second stage begins at 244.37 °C and ends at 557.62 °C.

Fig. 1. TG-DTA of FPAT.

The first and second stage shows 94.76 and 5.20% weight loss respectively. Two DTA peaks (endothermic) are observed at 104.79 °C and 241.12 °C. The first stage shows major weight loss and therefore various kinetic parameters viz. *E* (energy of activation), *n* (order of reaction), *Z* (pre-exponential factor), ΔS (entropy of activation) and *G* (free energy change) have been calculated for this stage only using Coats-Redfern (C.R.)⁶, MacCallum-Tanner (M.T.)⁷ and Horowitz-Metzger (H.M.)⁸ methods. The kinetic parameter data is given in Table 1. The values of *n*, *E*, *Z*, ΔS and *G* obtained by these methods are in good mutual agreement. The value of energy of activation *E* is a sufficiently high, lying in the range 17–24 kcal mol⁻¹, and it indicates that FPAT is thermally stable.

X-Ray diffraction studies :

FPAT has been characterized by powder X-ray dif-

fraction studies for predicting the crystal system present. There are 30 reflections (2θ) between 15.985° and 84.735° with maximum at $2\theta = 25.920$ and $d = 3.4345 \text{ \AA}$. The diffractogram is depicted in Fig. 2.

The cell parameters calculated are given in parenthe-

Table 1. Calculation of kinetic parameters by Coats-Redfern (C.R.), MacCallum-Tanner (M.T.) and Horowitz-Metzger (H.M.) methods

Compound : FPAT				
Stage	Kinetic parameter	C.R.	M.T.	H.M.
1	<i>n</i>	0.19	0.19	0.45
	<i>E</i>	17.936	17.693	23.917
	<i>Z</i>	2.025×10^5	3.07×10^{11}	2.68×10^8
	ΔS	-17.7526	-3.5177	-10.56
	<i>G</i>	20.0453	18.111	25.172

Units : *E*, kcal mol⁻¹; *Z*, s⁻¹; ΔS , JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹; ΔG , kcal mol⁻¹.

sis ($a = 5.5250 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 6.0553 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 11.4705 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = 106.767^\circ$, $\beta = 90.155^\circ$, $\gamma = 106.458^\circ$) and which are found to be in accordance with those required for a triclinic crystal system where $a \neq b \neq c$ and $\alpha \neq \beta \neq \gamma$.

Fig. 2. X-Ray diffractogram of FPAT.

Biological activity :

FPAT was tested for the evaluation of antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *K. pneumoniae* and antifungal activity against *A. niger* and *C. albicans* in DMF in the concentration range 2–16 µg/ml using serial dilution method. MIC values have been reported, which lie in the range 8–12 and 4–8 µg/ml for antibacterial and antifungal activity respectively (Table 2). Therefore, it is concluded that FPAT exhibits pronounced antifungal activity compared to antibacterial activity.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The solvents were dried according to standard procedures and

distilled before use. UV-Visible, IR and NMR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu A 600UV-Visible (ethanol), Shimadzu FT-IR 8400 (KBr) and Varian 300 MHz (CDCl₃) spectrometers respectively. Mass spectrum was recorded on Shimadzu GCMS QP 5050. Thermogram was recorded on V2 4F TA thermal analyzer at the heating rate 10 °C per minute in nitrogen atmosphere. X-Ray diffractogram was run in the range of 10–90° using a Philips PW-1710 diffractometer attached to a digitized computer along with graphical assembly where CuKα radiation source connected with a tube of Cu-NF 2 kV/20 mA was used.

Synthesis of 4-(p-fluorophenyl)-2-aminothiazole :

A mixture of *p*-fluoroacetophenone (0.05 mol), io-

Table 2. Antibacterial and antifungal activity of FPAT

Antibacterial activity				Antifungal activity			
Quantity of stock solution	Conc. in $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Growth (+)/inhibition (-) for		Quantity of stock solution	Conc. in $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Growth (+)/inhibition (-) for	
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>			<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
0.05	2	+	+	0.05	2	+	+
0.1	4	+	+	0.1	4	+	-
0.2	8	+	-	0.2	8	-	-
0.3	12	-	-	0.3	12	-	-
0.4	16	-	-	0.4	16	-	-
Control		+	+	Control		+	+

dine (0.1 mol) and thiourea (0.1 mol) was refluxed on water bath for 8 h and again 12–16 h after removal of condenser. The crude product was kept in contact with ether with occasional shaking for 48 h. The ether layer was removed and reaction product was treated with sodium thiosulphate solution to remove traces of iodine. The product was then boiled with water and then filtered. The filtrate was treated with concentrated ammonia to obtain the 4-(*p*-fluorophenyl)-2-aminothiazole, which was recrystallized from 50% ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Antibacterial and antifungal activity⁹ :

Eight test tubes containing 5 ml of sterile nutrient/sabourauds broth were inoculated with 0.02 ml of 24 h old culture of bacteria *S. aureus*, *K. pneumoniae* and fungi *A. niger* and *C. albicans* respectively. Different amounts of FPAT were aseptically added with the help of sterile pipettes from stock solution 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ to 5 ml quantities of respective media so as to reach the concentration from 1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ to 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. All test tubes were inoculated at 37 °C and at room temperature for bacteria and fungi respectively. Test tubes inoculated with organisms were observed for presence of turbidity after 24 and 48 h respectively. The lowest concentration of FPAT inhibiting the growth of test organism was determined as MIC value.

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